

PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS OF ORGANIZING THE PROCESS OF TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14748592>

Abstract

The article is devoted to the problems and prospects of organizing the educational process using digital technologies. Digital technologies help to organize training effectively and interactively, but their implementation may cause a number of problems. Among these problems, such issues as limited access to the Internet, fake news and lack of technical training are especially important. However, the prospects for digital education are very broad. New and innovative technologies, such as artificial intelligence and hybrid education, will allow in the future to organize the learning process more effectively and individually.

Keywords: digital technologies, interfaces, internet, fake news, artificial intelligence, hybrid education, virtual educational environment, mobile educational platforms, digital resources.

Entrance

The rapid development of new technologies and digital tools has led to major changes in the field of education. Today, digital technologies allow us to organize the educational process more effectively, but there are also a number of problems with their correct use. The article discusses the main problems and prospects for organizing the educational process using digital technologies.

Using digital technologies in the learning process

Digital technologies make teaching and learning more interactive and active. It allows students to access materials in a timely manner through mobile applications and online platforms. You can also make the learning process lively and interesting with the help of videos, animations and virtual simulations.

Problems

Internet access

One of the main problems in the implementation of digital education is the difficulty of connecting to the Internet. In particular, in developing countries and some regions, the lack of Internet connection and technical

infrastructure can limit students' access to digital education. This, in turn, reflects inequality in education and leads to the fact that students with no or limited access to information technology are left behind.

Data mining and fake news

The user has great opportunities to search for information in the digital environment. However, the reliability of the data in this regard can be questioned. The dissemination of false information and sources on the Internet can mislead students and prevent them from gaining accurate knowledge.

Technological skills of teachers and students

Not every student and teacher has the ability to use digital technologies correctly and effectively. They need special training, education, and skills to do so. This problem affects the quality of teaching and reduces the effectiveness of digital education.

News and innovations

Digital technologies bring new opportunities and innovations every day. For example, artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning algorithms help organize an individualized learning process in higher education. These technologies make it possible to determine the level of students' knowledge, provide them with sufficient material, and develop special educational programs based on it.

Hybrid education

Hybrid education (a combination of online and traditional education) will become more popular in the future. This type of education opens up new opportunities for students and teachers. Thanks to mobile devices and interactive platforms, students can continue learning anytime and anywhere.

Quality Digital Content

Creating quality, modern and interactive content will be crucial for digital education in the future. It not only provides students with information, but also helps them develop creative and analytical skills.

Digital Readiness of Teachers

It is important to train teachers in digital teaching methods and improve their digital skills. Teachers must be able to use modern educational tools and specialized platforms. To this end, educational institutions must organize continuous training and professional development for teachers.

Conclusion

Digital technologies allow to bring the field of education to a new level, but for their effective use it is necessary to find solutions to many problems. By using technologies correctly and applying them in the educational process, the quality of education and the opportunities of each student can be expanded in the future. The prospects of the digital education system are wide and deep, therefore its development will lead to positive changes in the field of education.

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